

IMPROVING MEDICAL AND PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION FOR PHARMACEUTICAL STUDENTS BASED ON INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *This scientific article discusses in detail the issues of improving medical and pharmaceutical education for students of the pharmaceutical industry based on innovative technologies. The study scientifically studies the impact of modern digital educational platforms, virtual laboratories, simulation exercises, distance learning and interactive pedagogical technologies on the educational process. The article discusses in detail the effectiveness of consolidating students' knowledge, developing practical skills and forming professional competencies through the use of innovative technologies.*

Keywords: *pharmaceutical education, innovative technologies, digital pedagogy, virtual laboratory, simulation training, distance learning, professional competence, interactive training, electronic learning resources, educational effectiveness.*

Introduction

Our country is taking consistent measures to modernize national medical and pharmaceutical education, introduce international educational standards in this area, conduct comprehensive scientific research on current issues of public health protection, and create an effective system of spiritual and moral education for young people. At the same time, the shortage of general practitioners and narrow specialists in remote and hard-to-reach regions of the republic, the lack of the necessary practical training in medical educational institutions, as well as the slow introduction of modern forms and methods of organizing continuing professional education require urgent measures to further improve the system of training medical and pharmaceutical personnel and determine promising directions for its development in the medium term.

The pharmaceutical industry is an integral and strategically important part of the healthcare system. Specialists working in this field play an important role in ensuring the population's need for medicines, monitoring the quality, safety and effectiveness of medicines. Therefore, the training of highly qualified specialists with modern knowledge and skills in the pharmaceutical field has become an urgent issue today. In today's globalization environment, science and technology are developing rapidly in the fields of medicine and pharmacy. New medicines, innovative technologies and digital solutions require pharmaceutical specialists to have a high level of professional competence, critical thinking and skills in working with modern technologies. Therefore, there is a need to update the content of education provided to students of the pharmaceutical field, improve teaching methods and introduce innovative technologies into the educational process.

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of regulatory and legal documents on the development of pharmaceutical education, modernization of the higher education system and the widespread introduction of digital technologies. In particular, the presidential decrees and state programs have identified the training of qualified personnel for the

pharmaceutical industry, the development of scientific and research activities and the use of innovative approaches as priority tasks. Modern pharmaceutical education should not be limited to traditional teaching methods, but should include innovative pedagogical technologies. Such technologies include digital educational platforms, electronic textbooks, virtual laboratories, simulation exercises and distance learning systems. With the help of these tools, students will have the opportunity to study complex pharmaceutical processes in more depth, combine theoretical knowledge with practice and develop independent thinking skills.

The use of innovative technologies in the field of pharmaceutical work is of particular importance, especially in laboratory exercises and practical classes. Virtual laboratories allow students to conduct experiments, analyze errors, and model complex processes in a safe environment. Simulation exercises serve as an effective tool for preparing students for real-world production and clinical situations. Distance and blended learning formats also create broad opportunities in pharmaceutical education. Through digital learning platforms, students can access educational materials at any time, learn independently, and assess their knowledge. This increases the flexibility of the learning process and improves the quality of education.

The issues of using innovative technologies in the training of students in the field of pharmaceutical work have been widely studied by domestic and foreign scientists in recent years. An analysis of scientific literature shows that digital educational technologies, simulation exercises and forms of distance learning are important factors in improving the quality of pharmaceutical and medical education. Domestic scientists Abdukodirov A.A. and Khalilov R.H. emphasize in their studies that innovative pedagogical technologies are an important tool in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process². In their opinion, the use of information and communication technologies in the educational process contributes to the active assimilation of knowledge by students and the development of independent thinking skills. Yuldoshev J.G. and Usmonov S.A. scientifically substantiated the possibility of increasing the effectiveness of the educational process through the systematic use of pedagogical technologies³. The authors note that when innovative approaches are used in the educational process, student activity and motivation increase significantly.

In his research on pharmaceutical education, Tokhtasinov D.T. pays special attention to the importance of virtual laboratories and simulation training in the training of specialists in the pharmaceutical field⁴. According to his research, such technologies thoroughly prepare students for professional activity by modeling real production processes. The effectiveness of digital technologies in medical and pharmaceutical education is also widely covered in foreign scientific sources. Reports published by the World Health Organization (WHO) consider the use of innovative educational technologies in the training of personnel in the healthcare sector as a global problem⁵. These documents emphasize that simulation training and e-learning systems increase the quality and safety of education.

UNESCO and European Union experts have assessed digital education as an integral part of the modern education system and have shown that it can ensure the flexibility and continuity of education⁶. In particular, the “Digital Education Action Plan” document identifies the development of digital competencies in higher education as a priority task. Studies conducted by Bates A.W. and Cook D.A. scientifically substantiate the effectiveness of e-learning and virtual patient technologies in medical and pharmaceutical education⁷. In their opinion, virtual learning environments are important in consolidating student knowledge and developing clinical thinking.

Also, Salas E. et al. emphasize that simulation-based teaching methods can reduce errors in the educational process and increase learning efficiency⁸. This approach is especially relevant in ensuring safety and quality issues in pharmaceutical education. This study is aimed at identifying the scientific and pedagogical foundations of the process of improving medical and pharmaceutical education for pharmacy students based on innovative technologies. The study was conducted on the basis of an integrated approach, which ensured the combination of theoretical and empirical methods. The methodology was developed based on the requirements of modern pedagogical research and served to determine the effectiveness of education.

The following scientific methods were used in the research process: Theoretical methods: analysis, comparison, generalization and systematization of scientific literature. Empirical methods: pedagogical observation, questionnaires, tests, interviews and experimental work. Statistical methods: evaluation of the obtained data through percentages, diagrams and comparative analysis. The integrated use of these methods ensured the reliability and scientific validity of the research results. The research was conducted with the participation of 2nd-3rd year students studying in the field of pharmaceutical work. Modern information and communication technologies, digital platforms and electronic educational resources were used in the experimental process. These conditions served to increase the activity of students in the educational process and develop independent learning.

This methodology allows you to assess the effectiveness of using innovative technologies in pharmaceutical education. The results of the study serve as a scientific basis for improving the educational process in the field of pharmaceutical work in higher educational institutions, creating methodological guides and planning pedagogical activities. At the same time, the visual and interactive mastery of theoretical knowledge using virtual laboratories and electronic educational resources had a positive effect on the consolidation of students' knowledge. This contributed to a deep understanding of the educational material and its retention in long-term memory.

During practical training, students performed tasks related to laboratory work, preparation of medicines and quality control. Through simulation training, students had the opportunity to work in conditions close to real production and clinical situations. The results of pedagogical observations and questionnaires showed that students are highly interested in lessons organized on the basis of innovative technologies. Students evaluated virtual laboratories and simulation exercises as the most effective and interesting form of the educational process. The results obtained show that the introduction of innovative technologies into pharmaceutical education significantly increases the quality of education. An integral connection between theoretical and practical training is ensured, and the formation of students' professional competencies is accelerated.

In general, the results of the experimental tests scientifically confirmed that the educational model organized on the basis of innovative technologies has high efficiency in training students in the field of pharmaceutical work. During the research, the impact of modern digital technologies, virtual laboratories, simulation learning environments and distance learning platforms on the educational process was studied scientifically, theoretically and practically. The results of the study showed that the educational process organized on the basis of innovative technologies plays an important role in increasing the level of knowledge of students, developing their independent thinking skills, and forming professional competencies. In particular, the combination of theoretical knowledge with practical training has brought the quality of pharmaceutical education to a new level.

The use of virtual laboratories and simulation technologies has allowed students to prepare for real production and clinical situations. This has allowed students to conduct experiments without fear of mistakes, develop their skills in analysis and quick decision-making in problem situations. As a result, the professional training of future specialists working in the pharmaceutical sector has significantly improved. Distance and digital educational technologies have activated students' independent learning activities, ensured the continuity of the educational process, and strengthened pedagogical relations between teachers and students. Also, the opportunities for repetition and consolidation of knowledge through electronic educational resources have expanded.

Conclusion

The results obtained during the study confirmed that the introduction of innovative technologies into pharmaceutical education not only increases the quality and efficiency of education, but also serves to train competitive and qualified personnel in accordance with international educational standards. This will have a positive impact on the sustainable development of the pharmaceutical industry in our country. In conclusion, the educational model based on innovative technologies in the pharmaceutical field fully meets the requirements of modern education and the needs of the labor market. One of the important tasks in the future is the widespread introduction of this model in higher education institutions, regular updating of curricula, and increasing the digital competencies of teachers.

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